

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION AND MESOSCALE MODELLING OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES UNDER HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT

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Keywords: Textile composite, Impact behaviour, Energy absorption, UHMWPE fibre, Mesoscale modelling

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the dynamic behaviour of textile composites subjected to high-velocity impact by a spherical steel projectile. The composite specimens were manufactured of UHMWPE plain weave fabrics and two different matrices, i.e. a rigid epoxy resin and a flexible epoxy resin. Impact tests were carried out on the prepared specimens at three different impact velocities to investigate the effects of matrix rigidity on the perforation resistance, energy absorption, and damage extent of textile composites. The experimental results revealed that the flexible matrix specimens always had higher perforation resistance and energy absorption capacity than the rigid matrix counterparts in the tested velocity range. The textile composites gradually changed from a membrane stretching mode to a plate bending mode as the matrix rigidity and thickness increased. It was found that the average energy absorption per ply was much higher in the membrane stretching mode when the composites were perforated. Moreover, a mesoscale finite element model of textile composites was developed based on the microscopic examination of the textile architecture.

1 INTRODUCTION

Textile composites are composed of fibre reinforcement being in the form of a textile fabric (woven, knitted, and braided) combined with a binding matrix. Generally, the fibre reinforcements are much stronger and stiffer than the matrix and largely determine the properties of textile composites. Whereas the binding matrix keeps the fibres in the designed position and orientation, acts as a load transfer medium between the fibres, and protects the fibres from environmental damage. Textile composites made of high-performance polymer fibres, e.g. aramid fibres and ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fibres, are increasingly used in body armour and ballistic helmets for protection against high-velocity impacts [1].

Because the fibre reinforcements are the principal load-bearing constituents and occupy higher volume fraction, the effects of reinforcement parameters, including ply orientation [2, 3], weave architecture [3-6], fibre hybridisation [7, 8], and reinforcement continuity [9], on the impact behaviour of textile composites have been extensively investigated. However, there is a paucity of studies on how the matrix properties influence the impact behaviour of textile composites. Lee et al. [10, 11] found the UHMWPE fabric-reinforced laminates with a rigid vinyl ester resin had higher ballistic limit velocity than those with a relatively flexible polyurethane resin, and it was deduced that the rigid resin prevented the yarn movement more and thereby forced the projectile to engage and break more yarns. In contradiction to the results found by Lee et al., Wang et al. [12] experimentally tested the impact behaviour of textile composites made of a UHMWPE woven fabric and different resin matrices and their results revealed that the composites having flexible matrices performed better in perforation resistance and energy absorption, but had a greater extent of deformation and damage than the counterparts with rigid matrices. Khodadadi et al. [13] compared the high-velocity impact behaviour

of Kevlar/rubber and Kevlar/epoxy textile composites, and it was found that the rubber matrix enhanced the energy absorption of composites by keeping them flexible. On the contrary, the thermoset epoxy matrix led to an inflexible composite that restricted the deformation of fabric reinforcement and had a negative effect on the ballistic performance.

Given the current uncertainty of the role of matrix and the paucity of existing literature, this work intends to investigate the effects of matrix rigidity on the perforation resistance, energy absorption, and damage extent of textile composites under high-velocity impact. To this end, composite specimens were manufactured using UHMWPE plain weave fabrics and two types of epoxy resins with different rigidities. Impact tests were carried out by firing a spherical steel projectile onto the prepared specimens in a velocity range of 100-200 m/s to analyse their perforation resistance and energy absorption. The damage status of each specimen was examined after the tests. In addition, a mesoscale finite element model of textile composites was developed at the yarn-level resolution with the purpose of gaining better insight into the yarn-matrix interaction mechanisms under impact loading.

2 SPECIMEN PREPARATION OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES

A plain weave fabric made of Spectra[®] 1000 fibres was used for making composite specimens in this study. Both the warp and weft yarns of the fabric contain 120 fibres and have a linear density of 650 denier (the mass in grams per 9000 metres), and the bulk density of the fibre material is 0.97 g/cm³. The properties of used fabric reinforcement are shown in Table 1. Two types of thermoset resins were selected as the matrix materials: one was the West System[®] 105 epoxy resin which has high strength and modulus after cure, and the other was Epopol[®] 7320, a urethane-modified epoxy resin having low strength and modulus but very high elongation. Both resins have low viscosity and long gel time at room temperature that allows the use of wet lay-up method for specimen fabrication. Table 2 lists the constituents of resin products and their cured mechanical properties obtained from the manufacturers.

Fibre	Tensile strength (GPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Failure strain (%)	Fibre density (g/cm ³)	Number of fibres in a yarn	Yarn denier	Weave style	Areal density (g/m ²)
Spectra [®] 1000	2.9~3.3	97~113	2.9~3.5	0.97	120	650	plain	95

Table 1: Properties of fabric reinforcement used for specimen fabrication.

Resin Type	Resin product	Hardener product	Mix ratio by weight	Density (g/cm ³)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Elongation (%)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Shore Hardness
Rigid	West System [®] 105	West System [®] 206	100:20	1.18	50.5	4.5	3172	D 83
Flexible	Epopol [®] 7320	Epolink LH 85	100:15	1.12	3.8	100	17	A 80-85

Table 2: Properties of resin matrices used for specimen fabrication.

The composite specimens were manufactured using a traditional wet lay-up method. Firstly, the raw fabric was cut into layers of desired dimensions. The cut fabrics were then impregnated with prepared resins and stacked layer by layer to the designed number of plies. In this experimental study, composite specimens consisting of 4, 8, and 16 plies of reinforcing fabrics were made with the two resins respectively. All the fabric layers were laid up in aligned orientation. The impregnated plies were then placed in a vacuum bag with an applied pressure of 90 kPa to cure at room temperature. After the resins were fully cured, the specimens were sectioned into rectangle targets of dimensions 250 mm × 150 mm for the following impact tests.

3 IMPACT TESTING

The impact tests were conducted using a single-stage gas gun, the details of which are shown in

Figure 1 (a). A spherical steel projectile with a diameter of 12 mm and a mass of 7.05 g was fired by the gas gun to impact the specimen centre at normal incidence. The projectile's impact velocity was controlled by the charged pressure in the reservoir and measured using two pairs of photoelectric sensors. The impact tests were carried out at three reservoir pressures of 2.5, 4.0, and 7.5 Bar resulting in nominal impact velocities of 112, 152, and 195 m/s (nominal impact energies of 44, 82, and 134 J). The composite specimens were secured into a target holder by clamping at the top and bottom sides over a width of 50 mm, which left a square part of 150 mm \times 150 mm in the middle, as shown in Figure 1 (b). The target's transient impact response was captured by a high-speed camera (Phantom v710) at 18,000 fps. The projectile's residual velocity of each test was measured from the calibrated video.

Figure 1: Experimental setup: (a) single-stage gas gun and (b) close-up of a clamped specimen.

4 MESOSCALE FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Finite element modelling is a critical tool to investigate the dynamic response of composite materials under high-velocity impact loading. On one hand, it is unfeasible to observe the complex interactions between fabric reinforcement and matrix from impact tests. To better understand the yarn-matrix interaction mechanisms, finite element modelling is an indispensable supplement to experimental work. On the other hand, once the validity of a finite element model is verified, it can take the place of the burdensome impact testing to some extent, especially for parametric studies, which could save a lot of time and expense. Due to the intricate architecture and multi-scale nature of textile composites, as well as the various deformation mechanisms of their constituent yarns and matrix, the modelling of textile composites is still an extremely challenging task. Therefore, a mesoscopic finite element model of a single-layer textile composite was developed by ANSYS LS-DYNA in this study.

The geometric parameters of the plain weave Spectra[®] fabric reinforcement were measured by microscopic examination, as shown in Figure 2. The yarn cross-sections were found to follow a lenticular shape, consisting of two symmetrical arcs. It was assumed that both the warp and weft yarns had the same cross-sectional shape and area, which remained constant all along the yarn path. The average thickness and width of yarn cross-section were 0.16 and 1.02 mm, respectively. As shown in Figure 2 (a), the yarn cross-section was meshed using 1 element through the thickness and 6 elements across the width. Non-uniform nodal thickness was specified for each element so that the mesh closely approximated the actual yarn cross-section. The centreline profile of yarn path in the used plain weave fabric closely followed a sinusoid with an amplitude of 0.08 mm and a wavelength of 3 mm. Both the warp and weft yarns were assumed to have the same degree of undulation or crimp, and the yarn path was modelled using a periodic sine function. The yarn path was meshed using 10 elements for a wavelength, and the eventual mesh of an individual yarn is illustrated in Figure 2 (b). Compared to the real textile structure, it can be seen that the yarn's undulating trajectory and cross-section were captured well by the finite element model.

Figure 2: Modelling scheme of (a) yarn cross-section and (b) undulating yarn path based on the real fabric structure.

Figure 3: Finite element modelling of single-layer fabric reinforcement and single-layer textile composite meshed using solid elements.

A full-scale mesoscopic finite element model of a single-layer textile composite is shown in Figure 3. The individual yarns within the fabric reinforcement were explicitly modelled as transversely isotropic continua and meshed using hexahedral solid elements. The matrix was meshed by tetrahedral elements and shared the nodal points with yarn elements at their interfaces.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 summarises the results of impact tests on textile composites with different matrices and layers under different impact velocities. The actual impact velocities were slightly different from test to test conducted at the same reservoir pressure. The negative sign in residual velocity indicates the projectile was stopped and then rebounded with a certain velocity in that test. According to the experimental results, all the composite specimens survived without perforation under nominal impact velocities of 112 and 152 m/s. When subjected to higher nominal impact velocity of 195 m/s, the 4-ply composites with both rigid and flexible matrices were perforated. The projectile had a lower residual velocity after perforating the 4-ply flexible matrix specimen (107 m/s) than the rigid matrix counterpart (154 m/s), indicating the flexible matrix specimen absorbed more energy. With the increase of reinforcement layers, the 8-ply and 16-ply flexible matrix specimens were able to resist nominal impact velocity of 195 m/s. Whereas the 8-ply and 16-ply rigid matrix specimens were perforated by the projectile under this impact velocity. Therefore, compared to the rigid matrix, the flexible matrix could improve the perforation resistance and energy absorption capacity of textile composites.

It is not surprising that the energy absorption of textile composites increased with the number of reinforcement layers, such as the rigid matrix composites as shown in Figure 4. All these specimens were perforated under the nominal impact velocity of 195 m/s. However, the energy absorption

averaged by the number of layers presents an opposite tendency. The energy absorption per ply decreased slightly from 4-ply to 8-ply specimens, and it dropped dramatically when the thickness increased to 16-ply. This sudden drop in the energy absorption per ply of the 16-ply specimen was due to the change of penetration mechanism as the thickness increased, which will be explained later. The thinner laminates appeared to work more efficiently for impact protection by absorbing more energy per ply. Consequently, it can be speculated that a target constructed by several spaced thin laminates may outperform a single laminate having the same total number of plies for energy absorption.

Matrix	Number of layers	2.5 Bar		4.0 Bar		7.5 Bar	
		Impact velocity	Residual velocity	Impact velocity	Residual velocity	Impact velocity	Residual velocity
Rigid	4	107	-31	154	-41	192	154
Flexible	4	96	-29	156	-31	197	107
Rigid	8	114	-15	150	-22	197	117
Flexible	8	121	-21	148	-25	196	-23
Rigid	16	118	-12	153	-10	196	86
Flexible	16	114	-8	152	-10	192	-16

Table 3: Summary of experimental results in terms of residual velocity vs. impact velocity (unit: m/s).

Figure 4: Comparison of total energy absorption and energy absorption per ply among rigid matrix composites with different reinforcement layers subjected to nominal impact velocity of 195 m/s.

By analysing the transient response of textile composites recorded by high-speed videos, it was found that the 4-ply specimens irrespective of resin matrix behaved in a membrane dominant mode sustaining the transverse impact loading with in-plane tensile stresses, which was qualitatively like the impact response of neat fabrics. With the increase of fabric layers, the 16-ply flexible matrix specimen still exhibited a membrane stretching mode similar to the thinner laminates. However, the 16-ply rigid matrix specimen was dominated by the plate bending mode where the impact loading was resisted by bending and shear stresses, which will be proved from the damage pattern later. In the plate bending mode, the specimens had less pronounced bulging and were perforated at an early stage. Therefore, the results indicate that the membrane stretching mode is preferable for energy absorption and perforation resistance of composites in the studied velocity range, since this mode allows the material to absorb energy and fail in tension, which is the most efficient way to utilise fibres with high tensile strength and toughness. When the matrix rigidity and the thickness increased, the laminate was gradually dominated by the plate bending mode, which causes the energy absorption efficiency and perforation resistance drop sharply.

Figure 5 demonstrates the photographs of all the specimens under transmitted light after 195 m/s impact, from which the extent and pattern of damage were visualised and compared. It should be mentioned that the planar damage area was the superposition of fibre breakage, matrix cracking, fibre/matrix debonding, and delamination from all the layers. The degree of blackness indicates the degree of damage through the thickness. It is clear that the 16-ply specimens showed different damage patterns. The 16-ply rigid matrix specimen exhibited a damaged area of oblong or ‘peanut’ shape with its long axis in the vertical direction and concentric to the impact point. The damage around the perforation region was more severe. This oblong damage shape has been commonly observed in rigid structural composites such as GFRP laminates [14] and CFRP laminates [15] subjected to high-velocity impact. There were severe shear cracks propagating from the perforation zone along the two reinforcing directions. However, a distinct damage pattern was found in the 16-ply flexible matrix specimen which had a lower bending stiffness and behaved in the membrane stretching mode. A damage strip consisted of matrix cracking, fibre/matrix debonding, and delamination was running along the vertical reinforcement direction up to the clamp edges. There was a visible cross-shaped damage zone, which was attributed to the stretching of orthogonal primary yarns. For the 4-ply and 8-ply specimens subjected to nominal impact velocity of 195 m/s, they all had a similar damage pattern to the 16-ply flexible matrix specimen. Because of the reduction of bending stiffness, all these laminates deformed in a membrane stretching mode.

Figure 5: Photographs showing the extent and pattern of impact-induced damage in all the specimens subjected to nominal impact velocity of 195 m/s.

6 FUTURE WORK

The developed finite element model of a single-layer textile composite is currently running, the results of which will provide detailed insight into the yarn-matrix interaction mechanisms under high-velocity impact. The simulation results will further explain the effects of matrix properties on the

impact behaviour of textile composites. Furthermore, the finite element models of multi-layer textile composites will be developed to investigate the effects of matrix properties on the delamination behaviour between layers.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A series of impact tests have been conducted on textile composites, and the effects of matrix rigidity on the energy absorption, penetration mechanism, and damage pattern have been discussed in this paper. The results showed that the flexible matrix specimens always had higher perforation resistance and energy absorption capacity than the rigid matrix counterparts. The impact response of textile composites was strongly dependent on the thickness and matrix rigidity. In general, as the thickness and matrix rigidity increased, the impact response of laminate gradually changed from a membrane stretching mode to a plate bending mode, which had inferior perforation resistance and lower energy absorbing capacity. The membrane stretching mode was a more effective way to utilise UHMWPE fibres because the material was highly stretched and failed in tension, and it was shown that the average energy absorption per ply was much higher in this mode. The results in this paper are indicative for engineering design of body armour and helmets because it provides a promising way to control the impact behaviour of textile composites for intended application by selecting the matrix material and thickness properly.

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